

Synthesis of Some 1,5-Benzodiazepines. Part III.

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A number of 1,3-diones were condensed with 3,4-diaminonitrobenzene, 3,4-diamino-chlorobenzene and 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid to form the corresponding substituted 1,5-benzodiazepines. The condensation of dibenzoyl methane with 4-nitro-*o*-phenylene diamine did not take place under Thiele-Steimmig conditions. The same was effected by modifying the reaction conditions.

1,5-BENZODIAZEPINES prepared in the earlier parts of this work^{1,2} do not have any substituent in the benzenoid part of the benzodiazepine nucleus. 1,4-Benzodiazepines which are used in medicine³ have either chloro or nitro group as a substituent at 7-position of the 1,4-benzodiazepine nucleus. 7-Substituted 1,5-benzodiazepines prepared by Levshina⁴ *et al.* have been found to possess cancerostatic activity. In this work, 1,5-benzodiazepines (III) are prepared by condensing 1,3-diones (II) with substituted *o*-phenylenediamines (I, X = Cl, NO₂, COOH).

It was observed that 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (I, X = NO₂) did not react with dibenzoyl methane (II, R = R' = Ph) under Thiele-Steimmig conditions⁵. Attempts to achieve the desired product by increasing the time of reaction were unsuccessful. The condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and 1,3-dione has been shown to be *pH* dependent^{6,7}. It was, therefore, thought to carry out this reaction at lower *pH*. 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mole) and dibenzoyl methane (0.01 mole) were condensed in a mixture of hydrochloric acid (2 ml) by refluxing the reaction mixture for 4 hr. The product was isolated as a hydrochloride and was treated with dilute ammonia. The compound obtained gave a positive test for a nitro group. It melted at 151°. But the compound obtained was found to be 2-phenyl-5-(6)

nitro-benzimidazole (IV), the identity of which was proved by elemental analysis. It was further established by its reduction to 2-phenyl-5-(6)-aminobenzimidazole (m. 285°). Bapat and Shrisat⁸ prepared the same compound (V) starting from 2-amino-4-nitro benzanilide.

They have reported the melting point of this compound as 290°. Though in this reaction ultimate product was benzimidazole, it was observed that benzodiazepine might have been formed as an intermediate, since the colour of the reaction mixture was intense violet in the beginning. In order to set the reaction conditions, the reaction was carried out with *o*-phenylene diamine and dibenzoylmethane at various temperatures because both the end products are known in this case. The reactions were carried out at 30°, 40°, 50°, 60° and 70°. Heating period was 4 hr in the last three cases, 4.5 hr in the second case and 5.5 hr in the first one. It was found that at temperatures 30°, 40° and 50° only 2,4-diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine was formed and at 60° and 70° only 2-phenyl benzimidazole was formed. The identity of both the end products was confirmed by melting points and mixed melting points. Yield of benzodiazepine was maximum at 50°. 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine was, therefore, condensed with dibenzoyl methane in a mixture of alcohol and hydrochloric acid for 4 hr at 50°. The product was isolated as a hydrochloride and a free base was obtained by treating the hydrochloride with dilute ammonia. The compound obtained melted at 236° and gave a violet colouration with hydrochloric acid. The compound gave a positive test for nitro group also. Elemental analysis of 2-phenyl-5-(6)-nitro benzimidazole, 2-phenyl-5-(6)-aminobenzimidazole and 7-nitro-2,4-diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine is given in Table I.

Infrared spectrum of 7-nitro-2,4-diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine in KBr disc showed the following characteristic bands.

Group	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)
1. ν N-H	3325
2. ν NO ₂	1520 and 1345
3. δ N-H	1580
4. ν C = N	1615
5. ν C-N <	1305
6. Aromatic ring breathing	1450
7. δ C-N (Aromatics)	
i) 2-Adjacent H atoms	820
ii) Monosubstituted phenyl	685 and 755

TABLE 1

Compound	M.P. °C	% Yield	% Found		% Required	
			C	H	O	H
2-Phenyl-5 (6)-nitro-benzimidazole	151	56	65.21	3.74	65.42	3.76
2-Phenyl-5(6)-amino-benzimidazole.	285	20	74.21	5.41	74.64	5.24
7-nitro-2, 4-diphenyl-1, 5-benzodiazepine.	236	36	72.86	4.42	73.02	4.39

TABLE 2

No.	Compound (IV)					R'	M.P. °C	% Yield	Found %		Required %	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	X				C	H	C	H
1.	H	H	H	H	Cl	Phenyl	162-3	46	75.81	4.59	76.24	4.54
2.	OH	H	H	H	"	"	189	42	72.36	4.51	72.72	4.33
3.	OH	CH ₃	H	H	"	"	178	44	72.95	4.81	72.23	4.71
4.	OH	H	H	CH ₃	"	"	204-5	32	73.01	4.78	73.23	4.71
5.	OH	H	H	Cl	"	"	176	38	66.02	3.76	66.14	3.67
6.	OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	"	198	31	73.62	5.21	73.70	5.07
7.	OH	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	"	204	29	73.55	5.15	73.70	5.07
8.	OH	H	H	H	"	2-Thienyl	109	29	64.49	3.75	64.68	3.69
9.	OH	H	H	CH ₃	"	"	208-10	27	65.41	4.21	65.48	4.09
10.	OH	H	H	Cl	"	"	150	29	58.38	3.10	58.91	3.10
11.	OH	H	H	H	"	3-Pyridyl	180	25	68.86	4.19	69.06	4.03
12.	H	H	H	H	COOH	Phenyl	260	53	77.42	4.81	77.65	4.70
13.	OH	H	H	H	"	"	130	22	73.94	4.35	74.16	4.49
14.	OH	CH ₃	H	H	"	"	250	30	74.19	4.75	74.59	4.86
15.	OH	H	H	CH ₃	"	"	120	25	74.26	4.75	74.59	4.86
16.	OH	H	H	Cl	"	"	193	33	67.51	3.82	67.61	3.75
17.	OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	"	280-2	31	74.81	5.32	75.00	5.21
18.	OH	H	H	CH ₃	"	2-Thienyl	259	22	73.25	4.79	73.78	4.86

Condensation of 1,3-diones with 4-chloro-*o*-phenylene diamine (II, X = Cl) and 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid (II, X = COOH) took place under Thiele-Steimig conditions. Melting points, elemental analysis and percentage yields of the benzodiazepines prepared are given in Table 2.

All the compounds have been sent for screening to the SK & F Laboratories, Philadelphia. Reports of activity are awaited.

Experimental

i) Preparation of 7-nitro-2,4-diphenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine :

A mixture of 3,4-diamino nitrobenzene (0.85 g), dibenzoyl methane (1.2 g), ethanol (15 ml) and con-

centrated hydrochloric acid (2 ml) was heated at 50° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with ether and water. The hydrochloride (violet) so obtained was neutralised with dilute ammonia solution. The product obtained was washed with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol-acetic acid mixture. M.P. 236°. Yield 0.7 g (36%).

2) Preparation of 2,4-disubstituted-7-chloro (or carboxylic acid)-1,5-benzodiazepines :

A mixture of ethanol (15 ml), glacial acetic acid (5 ml), substituted *o*-phenylene diamine (0.005 mole) and 1,3-dione (0.005 mole) was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate

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formed was crystallised from alcohol or alcohol-acetic acid mixture. Alcoholic solutions of all compounds produced violet colouration with hydrochloric acid, which slowly fades and eventually vanishes.

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